

Modelling of Alternative Pathways for Expansion of the Power Sector: Case Sierra Leone

- David Caulker, Ministry of Energy, Sierra Leone
- Date: 28th May 2024

Keywords: Energy System Modelling, Sierra Leone, Generation Expansion, Osemosys, Hydro, Natural Gas, import

Acknowledgements

I would first and foremost thank the Almighty God to have made it possible for me to attend and participate in this training workshop. I also want to thank to our trainers, Fernando Antonio Plazas, Pedro Peters and Simone Osei-Owusu.

I also want to express my sincere gratitude to the Climate Compatible Growth, United Nations Energy Commission for Africa, Ministry of Energy Ghana, the Ghana Energy Commission, Ghana Atomic Energy Commission, Ghana Institute of Management and Public Administration, and The Brew-Hammond Energy Centre at Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology as the organizers of the EMP-A, to have organised a magnificent training workshop that has deepened my understanding of energy planning particularly the Osemosys energy system modelling tool.

Last but not the least, I want to thank the CCG who have funded my participation to EMP-A by giving me and other Sierra Leoneans who had accompanied me to participate in this workshop for the development of the energy sector in Sierra Leone.

This material has been produced with support from the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme. CCG is funded by UK aid from the UK government. However, the views expressed herein do not necessarily reflect the UK government's official policies

Executive Summary

Sierra Leone is committed to increase electricity generation to 1 GW to meet future demand by 2030. this study investigated the challenges of electricity generation and what are the alternative technologies that would produce least cost electricity production. Using Osemosys optimisation tool, four scenarios were examined. The Business-as-Usual (BAU), Natural Gas Scenario (NGS), Electricity Imports (IMP) and Hydro (HYD). The investigations emphasised the current state of the power generation and the alternative technologies that would replace the Karpowership

Production of power increased in all scenarios notably electricity imports from Cote d'Ivoire, Guinea and Ghana. Increase in production power from natural gas powerplants have reduced the electricity production from the Karpowership at the NGS scenario. To meet the demand in 2050, Karpowership might reappear, but production might be in small amount. Additional capacities from natural gas and nuclear plants would totally phase out Karpowership in 2050.

In the NGS Scenario electricity imports dominated the technology mix from 2020 until 2050. This could be attributed to the lack of knowledge of the investments requirement for electricity imports from Cote d'Ivoire, Guinea and Ghana.

The HYD Scenario shows that Solar power plants account for the large production of electricity from 2040 to 2050. This is because, the hydro powerplants has reached their maximum limits of producing electricity.

Future work should focus on intensive data review to ensure accuracy and relevance of the model (Plaza- Nino). Thorough knowledge of prices of electricity imports in the region is vital to ensure accurate representation of the imports to avoid excessive contribution of electricity imports in power generation. Performing Flexibility assessment will provide valuable insights into the system's ability to adapt to increasing shares of variable energy sources (Plazas-Nino). Utilising this tool for teaching and research at the University of Sierra Leone will enhance the ability of the university to produce planning engineers crucial for the development of the sector.

A robust analysis related to the transition plans of replacing the Karpowership is worth investigating to determine alternative technologies for future electricity demand. Addressing this concern would save tens of millions of United States dollars that government is subsidizing to pay for the electricity production by Karpowership.

Osemosys energy planning can be used for teaching and research at the University of Sierra Leone to produce energy planning engineers for the development and sustainability of the energy sector.

1. Introduction

In accordance with the universal access to by 2030, the government is committed to produce 1 GW of electricity to meet the expected future demand. Access to modern energy services is a prerequisite for a nation to guarantee its citizens decent lives. In the foreseeable future, electricity demand is set to continue growing rapidly in developing countries (Olsson and Gardumi). As part of its commitment to produce 1 GW by 2030, the country is facing serious challenges in expanding the electricity production as well as developing the transmission and distribution networks which are inadequate and dilapidated. There is insufficient generation to meet peak demand in the Western Area of the country. Sierra Leone is one of the most electricity poor countries throughout sub-Saharan Africa with the country's energy needs remaining hugely underserved (Fields et al). The electricity supply is historically intermittent and unreliable, with frequent electricity blackouts, and currently around 5 million people are without access to electricity (Fields et al).

To meet the power demands, the Karpowership in the dry season produces the bulk of power of 65 MW when the Bumbuna Hydro Power produces less than 10 MW. In the contrary, Karpowership generates 25 MW in the wet season and Bumbuna Hydro Power produces close to 50 MW. Electricity imports from the Cote d'Ivoire of 27 MW is distributed among the other parts of the country as well as the capital in Freetown. The over reliance over the Independent Power Producers IPPs has caused serious financial burden on the utility the Electricity and Distribution Supply Authority (EDSA) that depends on government subsidies to meet its obligations. It is alongside this background that the study focuses on challenges of insufficient generation to meet demand and to explore alternative technologies that could provide the least generation of electricity option. Three main research questions were investigated that involve:

- What is the impact of natural gas power generation in the power sector?

- How does electricity imports affect the overall cost of the power sector?
- How does hydropower generation influence the power sector expansion in Sierra Leone?

Through a thorough assessment of these research objectives, this report aims to provide a comprehensive analysis by providing give insights into the challenges and options available for least cost expansion of electricity generation in the country.

2. Methodology

The Starter Data Kit (SDK) for Sierra Leone was used as the baseline model associated with the Reference Energy System (Cannone and Allington, 2021). The historical generation and the installed capacities from 2018 to 2023 (Kiley et al) were utilised to calibrate the model. Osemosys was the model chosen framework for the long-term analysis of the energy systems (Plaza- Nino, 2023). Osemosys is a bottom-up linear programming model that classifies the optimal development of the technology mix with emphasis of least cost technology and the satisfaction of all energy demands, among other constraints (Howells et. al, 2011)

Four scenarios were investigated that include: Business-as-Usual (BAU), Natural gas scenario (NGS), Electricity Imports (IMP) and Reduced Hydro Scenario (HYD). These scenarios are described in Figure 1.

- i. The BAU scenario is the reference that investigates the least cost option considering the same technologies and circumstances. It involves low penetration of new technologies such a electricity imports, nuclear, solar and thermal; no emissions constraints and the use of energy carriers based on historical trends
- ii. The NGS allows the model to decide the required capacity to generate power. all other technologies are constrained allowing natural gas to determine the production of electricity.
- iii. The IMP scenario emphasises into impact of natural gas in the technology mix when other technologies are constrained.
- iv. The HYD scenario decreased the capacity of hydro by deactivating other planned hydro projects for future interventions. The model was allowed to determine the production of electricity from this scenario.

Figure 1: Scenarios modelled

3. Results

The production of electricity has increased due to an increase in the consumption of electricity as it cut across all scenarios.

Figure 2 highlights the progressive increase in power generation reaching 41.6 PJ, 39.2 PJ, 59.7 PJ and 37.6 PJ in the BAU, NGS, IMP and HYD correspondingly. Both the BAU NGS and HYD show that Karpowership can generate electricity up to 2025

Figure 2: Power generation by technology in the years 2020 to 2050

Increase in production power from natural gas powerplants have reduced the electricity production from the Karpowership at the NGS scenario. To meet the demand in 2050, Karpowership might reappear, but production might be in small amount. Additional capacities from natural gas and nuclear plants would totally phase out Karpowership in 2050. In the NGS Scenario electricity imports dominated the technology mix from 2020 until 2050. This could be attributed to the lack of knowledge of the investments requirement for electricity imports from Cote d'Ivoire, Guinea and Ghana. The HYD Scenario shows that Solar power plants account for the large production of electricity from 2040 to 2050. This is because, the hydro powerplants has reached their maximum limits of producing electricity.

The power generation installed capacities increase in all scenarios from the BAU at 4.3 GW, NGS at 2.2 GW, IMP at 1.9 GW and HYD 6.8 GW as illustrated in Figure 3

Figure 3: Total annual installed capacity by technology in the years 2020 to 2050

In the BAU Scenario, the introduction of natural gas power plant by 2030, nuclear plant by 2040 and the renewables with emphasis on solar plants has account for the high installed capacity at about 4.3 GW to meet the energy needs of the country. In the NGS production of electricity is mainly from natural gas and hydro technologies. Karpowership is seen to produce limited electricity supply. In the IMP scenario natural gas plants dominates the growth with about 2 GW. However, after 2049, oil fired power plants are replaced by electricity imports, hydro and solar power generation.

In the HYD scenario, solar power generation is predominant due to the saturation of the hydro power. Hence solar power generation dominates technology mix to account for the 6.8 GW installed capacity.

In the BAU scenario the continued use of fossil fuels by power technologies resulted in the gradual increase in Co2 emissions. By 2050 these emissions will increase up to 2117 kt Co2 which is about twice the emissions in 2020. Both the NGS and HYD scenarios aligned in a linear trend up to 2030. Beyond 2030 the scenarios NGS and HYD tend to diverge and will reach 20422 ktC02 and 17972 ktC02 respectively as depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Total annual emissions from 2015 to 2050

The total discounted cost comprises of capita, fixed and variable costs of the development of the energy system. The total costs of the BAU, NGS, IMP and HYD scenarios are estimated at US \$ 7.61 billion, US \$ 6.8 billion, US \$ 7.64 billion and US \$ 7.56 billion respectively as given in Figure 4. The electricity import scenario is the least option which is not the best option. Reason is due to political instability that may arise in the countries where the imports will come from which are Cote d'Ivoire, Guinea and Ghana.

Figure 4: Total discounted costs from 2020 to 2050

5. Discussion

The results show that import of electricity offers the least cost of electricity generation. This option is not the best due to political instability that may arise from countries where the electricity imports come from. The government should prioritise hydro power generation to

provide base power. Nuclear power plant should also be considered for future projection as it is evident in 2040 when production will from nuclear plants.

The non availability of the prices of imports is a factor that shows high production of electricity as a least cost as compared to the BAU, NGS and HYD scenarios. This could be addressed if the correct data is available to determine whether electricity imports is the cheapest. its

Future work involving with this study should emphasis on several key aspects to enhance the understanding of our results. At first an intensive data review us crucial to ensure accuracy and relevance of the model (Plazas-Nino). In addition, detail study on the prices of electricity imports in the region is vital to ensure accurate representation of the imports to avoid excessive contribution of electricity imports in power generation. Performing flexibility assessment will provide valuable insights into the system's ability to adapt to increasing shares of variable energy sources [Fernando]. Utilising this tool for teaching and research at the University of Sierra Leone will enhance the ability of the university to produce planning engineers crucial for the development of the sector.

Lastly, a robust analysis associated with the transition plans of replacing the Karpowership is worth investigating to determine the alternative technologies for future electricity demand. Addressing this concern would save tens of millions of United States dollars that government is subsidizing to pay for the electricity production by Karpowership.

7. Conclusion

In summary in the pursuit of increase generation, Government should consider coal and nuclear power plants as part of the technology mix to meet the baseload demand in the BAU Scenario. To overcome this, natural gas power plants should be introduced which would reduce the impact of coal power plant. Electricity imports tend to produce the largest production of electricity by 2050. Though this option is the cheapest option, **but** this is not the best option due to energy security issues that may arise due to political instability that might occur in Cote d'Ivoire, Guinea and Ghana.

In conclusion, detail study on regional electricity import prices is crucial. In addition, further work needs to be carried out associated with the transitional plans for replacing the Karpowership that has caused serious financial burden of the government in tens of millions. Using the tool for teaching and research at the University of Sierra Leone can help to producing energy planners who would in future be a great asset in the sector as planning engineers.

References

Plazas-Nino: Modelling Decarbonization Pathways in the Power Sector in Developing Countries: The case of Colombia

Olsson, Gardumi. Modelling least cost electricity system scenarios for Bangladesh using OseMOSYS

Fields et al. Long Term Forecasting: A MAED application for Sierra Leone's Electricity Demand (2023-2050)

Cannone and Allington, 2021. Selected 'Starter Kit' energy system modelling data for Colombia. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-893706/v>

Kiley et al. CCG Sierra Leone – Data in Brief, 2024

Howells et. al, 2011. The Open Source Energy Modeling System An introduction to its ethos , structure and development. Energy Policy 39, 5850–5870.

